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Research Article

In Silico Screening Of Small Molecules Targeting Protein Kinases

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ABSTRACT

Background:

Computational modeling and simulation serve as valuable adjunct tools to traditional methodologies for evidence collection, including in-vitro and in-vivo studies, subject to FDA regulations. Over the past decades, a multitude of FDA-approved drugs with substantial anticancer efficacy have been discovered, primarily through the inhibition of various protein kinases.

Methods:

In the current investigation, five derivatives featuring a Benzamide moiety were selected, and in silico methodologies were employed to assess their potential as anticancer agents. These compounds underwent thorough scrutiny for their absorption, distribution, metabolism, excretion (ADME) properties, and drug-likeness characteristics. This study sought to identify novel compounds with anticancer potential, and their attributes were compared to those of the FDA-approved drug Cobimetinib.

Results:

It is seen that there is marginal shift after the energy minimization. In Errat value, it enhanced from 94.702 to 96.358. In protein analysis, Ramachandran plot showed 90.9% of amino acids resided in the most favored region. Z-score also shown a effective results. Ligand 5 has shown the similar binding energy, hydrogen bonds, halogen and Pi bond interactions with the standard drug.

Conclusion:

One of the derivatives that is Ligand 5 has shown greater resemblances in its interactions, encompassing hydrogen bonding, pi bonding, and halogen bonding with standard drug Cobimetinib.

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INTRODUCTION

Cancer represents a diverse spectrum of diseases arising from abnormal cellular changes that lead to uncontrolled cell proliferation and division¹. According to data from GLOBOCAN in 2020, it is estimated that roughly one in five individuals worldwide may develop cancer in their lifetime. Furthermore, one in eight men and one in eleven women succumb to this disease. The increasing aging population and various socioeconomic factors likely contribute to these rising statistics. One of the key challenges in developing effective anti-cancer drug candidates is the identification of suitable drug targets. These drug targets primarily consist of small molecules, typically characterized by their small size, often ≤ 500 Daltons. Small molecules have demonstrated notable success in targeting various key elements, including Receptors that bind to ligands on the cell surface and proteins located within the cell responsible for transmitting downstream Signaling pathways that promote the survival of cancer cells, proliferation, and metastasis. Within this category of small-molecule anti-cancer drugs, a significant portion comprises inhibitors of protein kinases³, with nearly a quarter of newly developed anti-cancer medications falling into this category. For example, in 2015 Gefitinib (Iressa), a specific inhibitor targeting the Epidermal Growth Factor Receptor (EGFR), gained approval from the USFDA for the treatment of non-small cell lung carcinoma. In 2005, the USFDA also approved Sorafenib (Nexavar; Onyx/Bayer), a multi-target tyrosine kinase inhibitor, used in the management advanced primary liver carcinoma and advanced renal cell carcinoma⁴. Additionally, Cobimetinib, a reversible inhibitor of mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) or extracellular signal-regulated kinase 1 (ERK1) kinase, received US FDA endorsement in 2015. MEK proteins act as critical regulators within the extracellular signal-related kinase pathway, known for its role in drives

cellular proliferation. Cobimetinib is indicated for patients with unresectable or metastatic melanoma when used in combination with vemurafenib. This combination has demonstrated resulted in enhanced apoptosis in in vitro studies and decreased tumor growth in murine models⁵. Significantly, an in-silico modeling study conducted by Cristina Catoni and colleagues identified Cobimetinib as a potential alternative MEK inhibitor for patients showing early resistance to dabrafenib/trametinib⁶.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Collection of data

The PubChem database functions as an extensive repository containing a diverse range of chemical compounds, including small molecules, Amino acids, nucleic acids carbohydrates, lipids, and small molecules⁷. Our acquisition of chemical structure data for the FDA-approved drug Cobimetinib involved two approaches: firstly, data was retrieved directly from PubChem; secondly, in instances where PubChem lacked the required structures, we manually created them using ChemSketch as depicted in Figure 1. Additionally, our research encompassed the exploration of various Cobimetinib derivatives, which were sourced from peer-reviewed scientific publications⁸. In our pursuit of protein-related investigations, we specifically focused on the amino acid sequence of OGG1_RAT, representing N-glycosylase/DNA lyase. To obtain this sequence, we referred to the Uniprot ID O702499. Subsequently, this FASTA sequence data served as the foundation for constructing a three-dimensional (3D) protein structural model¹⁰. To access protein structures in the PDB format, we utilized the PDB web server, a renowned resource hosting an extensive collection of over 134,000 biomolecular structures, derived from various techniques such as crystallography, NMR spectroscopy, and 3D electron microscopy¹¹. The

Open Babel software played a pivotal role in seamlessly converting various file formats essential for our research¹². Furthermore, for the critical task of energy minimization of the ligand¹³, we employed ArgusLab, a software package specializing in molecular modeling, graphical visualization, and drug design. To further enrich our investigative efforts, we harnessed the capabilities of Biovia Discovery Studio, an adaptable software application that facilitated interactive exploration and in-depth analysis of molecular structures in conjunction with pertinent data¹⁴.

Homology modeling and structural validation of protein

The three-dimensional (3D) configuration of the target protein was established using a homology modeling strategy, making use of the Swiss Model platform. The input for this process was the FASTA sequence of OGG1_RAT, a protein denoting N-glycosylase/DNA lyase. Within the Swiss Model, an exploration was conducted to locate the most suitable crystallographic structure from its database, serving as a template for the protein kinase modeling endeavor. This template selection was governed by a multifaceted assessment, incorporating elements such as sequence congruence, structural resolution, domain coverage, and the presence of a corresponding ligand binding site. Subsequently, the structural soundness of the resultant model was scrutinized and affirmed through an array of validation tools, including QMEAN4, ProSA, PROCHECK, and verify3D. These validation procedures are of paramount importance as they ensure the precision and dependability of the homology-modeled protein structure, affirming its suitability for further scientific inquiries.¹⁵⁻¹⁷

Protein and Ligand preparation

For the protein's preparation for molecular docking, Autodock Vina v.1.2.0. was utilized through a systematic procedure. Initially, all non-

essential elements, encompassing heteroatoms like water molecules and co-crystallized ligands, were methodically eliminated. Following this, the protein's structure was enhanced by the addition of hydrogen atoms to polar groups, and Gasteiger charges were computed to account for electrostatic attributes. Concurrently, all ligands engaged in the docking experiments also underwent a similar preparation, involving the addition of hydrogen atoms and charge assignment before the actual docking process. To ensure compatibility and consistency during the docking simulations, Open Babel, a versatile software tool, played a pivotal role in facilitating necessary format conversions. These methodical preparations were executed with the aim of optimizing the precision and dependability of the ensuing molecular docking analyses.

Defining binding site

The grid coordinates for the binding site were retrieved from BIOVIA Discover Studio, while the corresponding grid coordinates for the target were also sourced from the same platform, specifically Biovia Discovery. Comprehensive details pertaining to the grid coordinates for the various targets can be accessed in Table 1.

Molecular docking and analysis

Molecular docking investigations were carried out utilizing Autodock Vina v.1.2.0. In these experiments, both the protein and its corresponding derivatives underwent separate docking procedures. From the nine resulting binding poses, the one that closely resembled the native ligand binding conformation was singled out as the most pertinent outcome. To delve deeper into the ligands' interactions with the protein, two-dimensional (2D) depictions of amino acid interactions were generated. These visual representations were created through the application of BIOVIA Discovery Studio, offering valuable insights into the molecular-level binding interactions.

ADME And Drug Likeness Properties

The pharmacokinetic characteristics and adherence to Lipinski's Rule of Five for Cobimetinib and its five derivatives were assessed through the utilization of the Swiss ADME18 server. This comprehensive analysis sought to evaluate their pharmacokinetic attributes and their potential viability as candidates for drug development, with a focus on their alignment with Lipinski's Rule of Five. This rule delineates criteria associated with oral bioavailability and permeability, which are critical factors in assessing drug-like properties.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

A quality control (QC) analysis was executed to evaluate the structural integrity of the protein model. The Errat analysis was applied to assess the protein structures, resulting in an enhancement of overall quality from 94.702 to 96.358 after energy minimization. The Errat analysis entails two distinct regions, one at 95% and another at 99%. The protein's sequence comprises 345 amino acids, and in its pre-energy minimized state, amino acid 41 extended into the 99% region, as depicted in Figure 2.a. For protein analysis, the SWISS modeling server was utilized, and a Ramachandran plot, as presented in Figure 3.a, was generated for both the pre-energy minimized and post-energy minimized states. The outcomes indicated minimal alteration in the distribution of amino acids within favored, allowed, generously allowed, and disallowed regions. Approximately 90.9% of amino acids resided in the most favored region. A high-quality protein model is expected to possess over 90% of its residues in the most favored regions, as determined by an assessment of 118 structures with resolutions better than 2.0 Angstroms with an R-factor below 20%. Figure 3.c exhibited the Z-score, which was determined to be -10.19. A marginal shift in the Z-score value was observed in the post-energy minimized state, as detailed in Table 1. The energy levels of amino

acids were evaluated for both low and high energy states using ProSA, as illustrated in Figure 3.d. Furthermore, Swiss ADME analysis was conducted for the ligand and its derivatives to assess their absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion (ADME) attributes. The results are depicted in Figure 4 and extensively documented in Table 3. Notably, all ligand derivatives adhered to Lipinski's Rule of Five, except for a violation related to molecular weight. These ligand derivatives demonstrated substantial gastrointestinal absorption, with the exception of Cobimetinib. Additionally, all ligand derivatives, except Cobimetinib, exhibited impermeability to the blood-brain barrier (BBB). The calculated iLogP values for all ligand derivatives remained within acceptable limits. Cobimetinib displayed the highest iLogP value at 3.36, while Ligand-4 recorded an iLogP value of 2.90. Molecular docking experiments were conducted between the modelled protein and the ligand derivatives, utilizing grid coordinates as detailed in Table 2. The binding energies for Ligands L1, L2, L3, L4, L5, and Lstd were computed and are presented in Table 4. Notably, Ligand L5 exhibited a binding energy profile analogous to that of the standard Cobimetinib, with similar hydrogen, halogen, and Pi bond interactions.

CONCLUSION:

The aim of this study was to examine the most favorable binding energies among the ligand derivatives and their interactions with the modelled protein OGG1_RAT. Ligand 5 exhibited significant resemblances in its interactions, encompassing hydrogen bonding, pi bonding, and halogen bonding, when compared to the reference standard Cobimetinib. Furthermore, Ligand 5 displayed a binding energy of -6.9. A series of analytical procedures, including quality control (QC) analysis, energy minimization, absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion (ADME) screening, as well as molecular docking, were

systematically conducted to establish the conclusions presented in this study. These collective investigations not only substantiate the findings but also underscore the potential of Ligand 5 as a promising candidate, evident in its binding interactions and binding energy with the OGG1_RAT protein.

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Figure 1: 2D structures of Ligand. *L1; L2; L3; L4; L5 and LStd Cobimetinib

a.

b.

Figure.2: a) and b) Illustrates the Errat analysis of modelled protein. The overall quality has been increased post energy minimization from 94.702 to 96.358

Figure.3: a) Ramachandran plot showing 90.9% are in favored region. b) Statistical results of Ramachandran plot. c) Z-score is found to be -10.19 which has increased post energy minimization. d) Illustration of low and high energy in amino acids.

Figure.4: L1, L2, L3, L4, L5, L std shows the physicochemical radar of ligand and its derivative using Swiss ADME.

Figure.5: a, b, c, d Docked complex of ligand and its derivatives.

Figure: 5: e. Docked complex of ligand derivative and f. Standard drug Cobimetinib.

Table.1: Structure validation results of homology model performed with various servers.

S. No	Server	Parameters	Values
1	PROSA	Z-SCORE	-10.19
2	PROCHECK	Residues in most favored region	90.9%
3	Save Server	Errat analysis: Overall Quality factor	96.358

Table.2: Grid coordinates of targets used for docking.

PDB ID	Center coordinates	Size coordinates
6g3y.1.A	center_x = 5.424926	Size_x = 20
	center_y = 11.585963	size_y = 20
	center_z = 27.783741	size_z = 20

Table.3: ADME prediction results of Compounds and physiochemical properties.

Physiochemical Properties	Ligand-1	Ligand-2	Ligand-3	Ligand-4	Ligand-5
Molecular weight(gm/mol)	560.28	563.31	553.27	539.24	567.25
No. of rotatable bonds	9	9	11	11	9
H-bond acceptors	8	7	8	9	9
H-bond donors	3	3	3	4	3
TPSA1(A ²)	100.13 Å ²	90.90 Å ²	100.13 Å ²	112.41 Å ²	109.36 Å ²
Water Solubility	-4.92	-5.11	-4.69	-4.62	-5.01
Lipophilicity i(LogP)	2.99	3.21	3.05	2.90	3.17
GI absorption	High	High	High	High	High
BBB Permeant	No	No	No	No	No
CYP1A2*	No	No	No	No	Yes
CYP2C19*	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
CYP2C9*	No	No	Yes	No	Yes
CYP2D6	No	Yes	No	No	No
CYP3A4*	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes
P-Gp2 substrate	No	No	No	No	No

Table.4: Binding interactions of different ligands with the modeled target protein.

Protein	Ligand	Binding energy	Hydrogen Bonds
OGG_1 RAT	L1	-7.6	HIS A:270, ASP A:268
	L2	-8.0	ASP A:268, HIS A:270
	L3	-6.9	LYS A:249, ASN A:150, GLY A:42 , ILE A:152, SER A:147
	L4	-7.6	ILE A:152 , ASP A:268, ASN A:150, HIS A:270, SER A:147, GLY A:312.
	L5	-6.9	ILE A:152 , HIS A:270, ASN A:150, LYS A:249, SER A:41
	Lstd	-8.2	ILE A:152, GLY A:42